

'The 2024 Student Protests in Bangladesh: A Political Analysis of the Crisis in Autocracy Vs Democracy'

Abstract

The 2024 student protests in Bangladesh represent a critical juncture in the nation's political trajectory. This research paper explores the underlying causes, development, and implications of these protests, particularly focusing on the role of Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina. The study investigates the thesis that these protests symbolize a struggle for Bangladesh's political destiny, with PM Hasina purportedly seeking to transform the country from an autocracy to a totalitarian regime. By analyzing the protests across various universities and divisions, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive political analysis of the ongoing crisis.

Introduction

The political climate in Bangladesh has become increasingly volatile, marked by widespread student protests that erupted in July and August 2024. These protests, driven by dissatisfaction with the current government, highlight significant socio-political issues and raise questions about the country's future direction. This research examines the causes, manifestations, and potential outcomes of the 2024 student protests, considering the role of Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina and her administration.

Background

Historical Context:

Since its independence in 1971, Bangladesh has experienced numerous political upheavals. The country's political landscape has been shaped by power struggles between major parties, notably the Awami League and the Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP). Sheikh Hasina, the leader of the Awami League, has been a dominant political figure, serving as Prime Minister since 2009.

Previous Student Movements:

Student movements have historically played a pivotal role in Bangladesh's political scene. From the Language Movement of the 1950s to the anti-autocracy protests of the 1990s, students have often been at the forefront of political change. The current protests continue this tradition, signaling a significant moment in the nation's history.

Causes of the 2024 Student Protests

Economic Challenges:

Bangladesh's economy, despite notable growth, has faced significant challenges, including high unemployment rates, particularly among the youth. Rising living costs and limited job opportunities have exacerbated frustrations, driving students to the streets.

Educational Issues:

The quality and accessibility of education have been persistent concerns. Students have protested against inadequate facilities, high tuition fees, and lack of job prospects post-graduation. The government's failure to address these issues has fueled the current unrest.

Political and Human Rights Concerns:

Allegations of corruption, human rights abuses, and autocratic governance under Sheikh Hasina have further inflamed dissent. The government's suppression of opposition voices and restrictions on freedom of speech have contributed to the growing discontent among students.

["Bangladesh: Witness testimony, video and photographic analysis confirm police used unlawful force against protesters". *Amnesty International*. 17 July 2024.](#)

The Role of Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina

Governance Style and Policies:

Sheikh Hasina's tenure has been marked by a consolidation of power and a centralization of authority. Her administration has been accused of undermining democratic institutions and eroding civil liberties. Critics argue that her governance style is increasingly autocratic, with tendencies towards totalitarianism.

Public Perception and Opposition:

Public opinion on Hasina's governance is polarized. While her supporters commend her for economic progress and infrastructural development, her detractors highlight issues of corruption, nepotism, and human rights violations. The opposition, led by the BNP and other parties, has capitalized on these grievances, supporting the student protests.

Manifestations of the Protests Across Universities and Divisions

Dhaka University and Prominent Institutions:

Dhaka University, traditionally a hub of political activism, has been at the epicenter of the protests. Students from other prominent institutions such as Jahangirnagar University,

Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET), and Chittagong University have also played crucial roles.

Regional Dynamics:

The protests have spread to various divisions, including Chittagong, Rajshahi, Khulna, Barisal, Sylhet, Rangpur, and Mymensingh. Each region has its unique socio-political dynamics, but the overarching grievances against the government have united the student movement.

Political Implications:

Autocracy vs. Totalitarianism

The current crisis can be framed within the theoretical context of autocracy and totalitarianism. Hasina's governance style exhibits characteristics of both, with increasing control over the political sphere, suppression of dissent, and efforts to maintain power at all costs.

The Battle for Political Destiny

The 2024 student protests symbolize a broader struggle for Bangladesh's political future. The outcome of this crisis could determine whether the country moves towards greater authoritarianism or reclaims a more democratic trajectory. The protests reflect a clash between the desire for democratic freedoms and the government's attempts to maintain control.

Civilian Casualties During the Protests

In the midst of the July-August 2024 protests, reports indicate that the government's response through police, army, and other law enforcement agencies resulted in significant civilian casualties. According to human rights organizations and local media reports, approximately 300 civilians, including students, common people, and children, were killed during the crackdowns on protests. The heavy-handed approach by the government has drawn widespread condemnation from both national and international observers, further intensifying the crisis. ["At least 32 children killed in Bangladesh violence"](#). [UNICEF](#). 2 August 2024. Retrieved 2 August 2024.

[List of casualties](#) ["Bangladesh mourns some 200 deaths as student protests wind down and thousands are arrested"](#). [Washington Post](#). 31 July 2024.

1. Md Farooq (32), furniture shop employee, shot dead, Chittagong Medical College Hospital, Muradpur, Chittagong, 16 July.
2. Md Wasim (22), student of Chittagong College, died of injuries, Chittagong Medical College Hospital, Muradpur, Chittagong, on 16 July.
3. Faisal Ahmed (20), student, shot dead, Chittagong Medical College, Muradpur, Chittagong, 16 July.
4. Md. Shahjahan (25), cloth shop worker, died of head injury, Brother Noorun Nabi, Science Laboratory, Dhaka, July 16.
5. Sabuj Ali (25), student, Dhaka College, died of head injury, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, opposite Dhaka College, on 16 July.
6. Abu Saeed (22), student, shot dead, in front of BRU, 16 July.
7. Asif (23), student, shot dead, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
8. Sakil, shot dead, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Uttara, July 18.
9. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
10. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
11. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
12. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
13. Unknown, student, shot dead, Bangladesh Kuwait Maitri Hospital, Uttara, 18 July.
14. Unknown, student, shot dead, Bangladesh Kuwait Maitri Hospital, Uttara, 18 July.
15. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Bangladesh Kuwait Maitri Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
16. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Bangladesh Kuwait Maitri Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
17. Unknown, killed by gunfire, Red Crescent Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.
18. Farhan Faiz Ratul (17), student, shot dead, City Hospital, Uttara, on 18 July.

19. Hasan Mehedi, journalist, Dhaka Times, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Kajla, Jatrabari, 18 July.
20. Wasim Sheikh (30), died of head injury, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, Fish Store, 18 July.
21. Nazmul Kazi (20/22), died of injuries, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 18 July.
22. Mohammad (20), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Azimpur, 18 July.
23. Unknown (30), rickshaw puller, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 18 July.
24. Unknown, Faraji Hospital, Rampura, 18 July.
25. Unknown, Faraji Hospital, Rampura, 18 July.
26. Unknown (18), student, shot dead, Chittagong Medical College, Bahaddarhat, 18 July.
27. Unknown (22), student, shot dead, Chittagong Medical College, Bahaddarhat, 18 July.
28. Ashabul Yamin (20), student, MIST, Mirpur, shot dead, Enam Medical College, Savar, on 18 July.
29. Tahmid Tamim (15), school student, Narsingdi, shot dead, 100 Bed Hospital, Narsingdi, 18 July.
30. Eamon Mia (22), student, Government Satirpara School, shot dead, Narsingdi Sadar Hospital, Narsingdi, on 18 July.
31. Deepto Dey (21), student, Madaripur College, Lekpar, Madaripur, on July 18.
32. Raudra Sen (22), student, SUST, Police Lake Area, Surma Gate Point, on 18 July.
33. Manik Mia (40), rickshaw puller, shot dead, Rangpur Medical College Hospital, behind police station, 18 July.
34. Sakil Hossain (22), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 18 July.
35. Imran (24), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 18 July.
36. Abdullah (15), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 18 July.
37. Saimun Siam (25), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 18 July.
38. Ismail (35), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, 18 July.
39. Khalid Saifullah (18), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Azimpur Staff Quarters, Dhaka, 18 July.
40. Dulal Matbar, microbus driver, shot dead, Merul Badda, 18 July.
41. Zillur Rahman (17), student, Imperial College, shot dead, BRAC University Area, 18 July.
42. Raudra Sen (20/22), student, Lekpar, Akhalia, on 18 July.
43. Hussain, shot dead, Banshtala, Badda, 18 July.
44. Md. Sakil Hossain, Journalist, Daily Bhorer Awaz, Gacha Thana, Gazipur, 18 July.
45. Rakib Hossain (22), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Aftabnagar, 19 July.
46. Gani Sheikh (45), labourer, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shahjadpur, 19 July.
47. Unknown, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Kajla.
48. Sohag (19), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shahjadpur, 19 July.
49. Arif (18), shopkeeper, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, Kajla, 19 July.
50. Santu (20), shopkeeper, shot dead, Jatrabari, Kajla, 19 July.
51. Rabbi (27), shot dead, Abu Taleb School, 19 July.
52. Adud (40), shot dead, China Building, Newmarket, 19 July.
53. Pavel (25), shopkeeper, Shahbagh, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Paltan, 19 July.
54. Mubarak (32), shopkeeper, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Kadmatoli, 19 July.
55. Akram Khan Rabbi (24), student, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
56. Jihad (22), student, shot dead, Shanirakhra, 19 July.
57. Dulal Mohammad Dolan (40), banker, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Azimpur, 19 July.
58. Unknown (18), shot dead Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Batara, on 19 July.
59. Omar Farooq (23), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Laxmibazar, Dhaka, 19 July.
60. Abdul Wadud, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
61. Maruf Hossain (25), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
62. Mehdi Hasan (20), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
63. Saiful Islam, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
64. Unknown (25), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
65. Rabiul Islam (30), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
66. Ismail, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
67. Kamal Mia/Jalal Mia (45), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
68. Naveen Talukder, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
69. Eamon (25), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
70. Sohail (35), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
71. Unknown (22), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
72. Shaun (24/25), student, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, China Building, Newmarket, 19 July.
73. Parvez (23), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
74. Mamun Sardar (34/27), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
75. Shovan (25), China Building, Newmarket, July 19.
76. Redwan (22), student, Bangabandhu, shot dead, Kamarpara, 19 July.
77. Sharif (23), student, Bangabandhu, shot dead, Kamarpara, 19 July.
78. Raid (22), student, Bangabandhu, shot dead, Kamarpara, 19 July.
79. Rana (15), shot dead, 19 July.
80. Sohag Mollah, PA, Mayor, Uttara, 19 July.
81. Munsur (40), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
82. Sharif, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
83. Russell, student, Faraji Medical College Hospital, July 19.
84. Unknown, Faraji Medical College Hospital, July 19.
85. Unknown, Faraji Medical College Hospital, July 19.
86. Unknown, B Life H, 19 July.
87. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
88. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
89. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
90. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
91. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
92. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
93. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
94. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
95. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
96. Unknown, SSMCH, 19 July.
97. Unknown, Mugda Medical College Hospital, July 19.
98. Unknown, Mugda Medical College Hospital, July 19.
99. Unknown, Mugda Medical College Hospital, July 19.
100. Unknown, Mugda Medical College Hospital, July 19.
101. Unknown, Uttara, 19 July.
102. Sajjal Hossain (28), Rangpur, 19 July.
103. Meraj (40), Rangpur Medical College, 19 July.
104. Unknown, Rangpur Medical College, 19 July.
105. Mozammel (32), Rangpur Medical College, 19 July.
106. Mokhlesur Rahman Milan (25), Rangpur, 19 July.
107. Moun (25), Rangpur, 19 July.
108. Abdur Rashid (70), hold/raid, Fazlul Haque Road, Sirajganj, 19 July.
109. Siam (16), shot dead, Amtala Mor, Bogra, 19 July.
110. Ehsanul Haque (22), July 19.
111. ATM Torab (30), journalist, Sylhet, 19 July.
112. Unknown, Narsingdi, 19 July.
113. Sagar, (16), Mymensingh, July 19.
114. Al Amin (24), Daraz employee (student), Enam Medical College Hospital, Savar, 19 July.
115. Shahjalal (26), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
116. Parvez (23), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.

117. Jewel (25), Ansar, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dainik Banglar Mor, 19 July.
118. Ifti (16/14), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, in front of Anabil Hospital, Kajla, on 19 July.
119. Unknown (41), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
120. Shakeel (22), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
121. Unknown (30), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
122. Rajib (30), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 19.
123. Al Amin (18), student, shot dead, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Kamarpara, Uttara, on 19 July.
124. Naima Sultana (15), student, shot dead, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, Home, on 19 July.
125. Nurul Islam, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
126. Jamal Mollah, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
127. Unknown, Uttara Modern Medical College Hospital, 19 July.
128. Unknown, Crescent Hospital, July 19.
129. Md. Siam (18), shot dead, July 19.
130. Hriday Mir (18), shot dead, 19 July.
131. Sujan Mia (17), shot dead, 19 July.
132. Amjad Hussain (22), shot dead, 19 July.
133. Unknown, 19 July.
134. Asif Iqbal (29), X student, Magura, Dhaka, 19 July.
135. Mottakin Billah (25), Magura, Dhaka, 19 July.
136. Raju, Magura, 19 July.
137. Atiqul Islam (32), shot dead, Patuakhali, Mirpur-10, 19 July.
138. Unknown (20), Mitford Hospital, Laxmibazar, Dhaka, 19 July.
139. Unknown (40), Mitford Hospital, Dhaka, July 19.
140. Rohan (20), student, HSC candidate, Mitford Hospital, Dhaka, Jatrabari, 19 July.
141. Russell, Mitford Hospital, Dhaka, Jatrabari, 19 July.
142. Bandhan (19), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, 19 July.
143. Md Zubair (40), Kuwait Bangladesh Friendship Hospital, 19 July.
144. Md. Roman (25), Staff Hospital, LabAid, 19 July.
145. Asiqul Islam Ilyas Asiq (15), Madrasa student, shot dead, Banshri Hospital, Banshri, Dhaka, 19 July.
146. Roman Bepari (32), truck driver, shot dead, Madaripur, Charmogoria, Sarabik Petrol Pump, New Bus Station, 19 July.
147. Tauhid Sannamat (20), madrasa student, shot dead, Madaripur, Charmogoria, Sarbik Petrol Pump, New Bus Station, 19 July.
148. Md Imran Khalifa (33), private school teacher, shot dead, Khilbari Tech, Shahjadpur, Dhaka, 19 July.
149. Alamgir Sheikh (35), driver, shot dead, BTV Centre, BTV, 19 July.
150. Monir (18), painter, shot dead, Banshtala, Badda, on July 19.
151. Hasnain (25), dishline employee, shot dead, Mohammadpur, 19 July.
152. Safqat Sameer (11), madrasa student, shot dead, Kafrul, Mirpur, 19 July.
153. ASI Moktadir (48), Tourist Police, gang beating, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra, Rayerbagh, Jatrabari, 20 July.
154. Naik Ghiyasuddin (58), DMP Police, gang-rape Dhaka Medical College Hospital, under footoverbridge, Rayerbagh, 20 July.
155. Imam Hossain Tajim (19), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra and Jatrabari area, 20 July.
156. Jisan (33), water vendor, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra and Jatrabari area, 20 July.
157. Yunus Ali Shaon (25), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra and Jatrabari area, 20 July.
158. Yusuf Mia Ilyas Sanwar Hossain (35/40), rice trader, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra and Jatrabari area, 20 July.
159. Habib Sardar (30/40), CNG driver, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra and Jatrabari area, 20 July.
160. Kamrul Mia (27), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Mirpur, July 20.
161. Sohail (35/23), mobile shop employee, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Kadmatoli, 20 July.
162. Arif (35), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Signboard, Narayanganj, Shanirakhra, 20 July.
163. Unidentified child (10), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Signboard, Narayanganj, 20 July.
164. Abdul Hannan, (35), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Batara, Dhaka, 20 July
165. Shubo (16), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Batara, Dhanmondi, Dhaka, 20 July.
166. Abdullah Al Abir (23), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Batara, Dhaka, 20 July.
167. Unknown, shot dead, S Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, 20 July.
168. Rakib (19), student, shot dead, Mymensingh Medical College, Kaltapara, Gouripur Upazila, 20 July.
169. Zubair (21), student, shot dead, Mymensingh Medical College, Kaltapara, Gouripur Upazila, 20 July.
170. Md. Biplab (18), student, shot dead, Mymensingh Medical College, Kaltapara, Gouripur Upazila, July 20.
171. Saiful Islam (42), farmer, shot dead, Mymensingh Medical College, Amakanda Bridge, Phulpur Mymensingh, 20 July.
172. Korban Ali (60), poultry trader, shot dead, Enam Medical College, Savar, Dhaka, 20 July.
173. Mehdi Hasan (24), mason, shot dead, Enam Medical College, Bazar Road, Savar, Dhaka, 20 July.
174. Shad Mahmud Khan (14), Madrasa student, shot dead, Enam Medical College, Savar, Dhaka, 20 July.
175. Roni (27), rickshaw puller, shot dead, Enam Medical College, Savar Bus Stand, Dhaka, 20 July.
176. Md Raihan (18), garment worker, shot dead, S Tajuddin AMCH, Bordbazar Area, Chandna Chowrasta, 20 July.
177. Nurul Amin (21), daily labourer, shot dead, S Tajuddin AMCH, Telepara area Joydevpur, Bordbazar, 20 July.
178. Tipu Sultan/ Md: Tipu/Zahirul Islam (27/48) gang beating, Shibpur Hospital, College Gate, Shibpur, Narsingdi, 20 July.
179. Mubarak Ali (13), shot dead, Greenlife Hospital, Panthpath, Dhaka, 20 July.
180. Hasan Mia (45), daily labourer, shot dead, Meherpara, Narsingdi, 20 July.
181. Md. Mehdi (20), student, shot dead, Neyar Pritam Tower, Shimrail, Siddhirganj, July 20.
182. Md Hriday (28), shot dead, Sugandha Private Hospital, Neyar Pritam Tower, Shimrail, Siddhirganj, July 20.
183. Md Shaheen/Manik (23), Hotel Manager, shot dead, Sugandha Private Hospital, Neyar Pritam Tower, Shimrail, Siddhirganj, 20 July.
184. Md. Sajal (22), shot dead, Sugandha Private Hospital, Pritam Tower, Shimrail, Siddhirganj, July 20.
185. Minarul Islam (25), garment worker, shot dead, 300 Seat Hospital, Narayanganj, Neyar Pritam Tower, Shimrail, Siddhirganj, 20 July.
186. Rajib Hossain (30), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital Kadmatoli, 20 July.
187. Maya Islam (60), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, in front of Her House, Rampura, 20 July
188. Amjad Hossain (22/17), student, shot dead, Itakhola Highway Police Station, 20 July.
189. Hriday Mir (15), student garage mechanic, shot dead, Itakhola Highway police station, July 20.
190. Sujan Miah (17), student/VAT/Laguna driver, shot dead, Itakhola Highway police station, July 20.
191. Siam Ahmed (19) student, shot dead, Itakhola Highway police station, July 20.
192. Unknown (middle age), shot dead, Velanagar Narsingdi, 20 July.
193. Ashiq Mia (15), shot dead, Madhavadi, Narsingdi, July 20.
194. Humayun Kabir (25), shot dead, Board Bazar area, Gazipur, 20 July.
195. Tanay Das/Tanmay Das (28), shot dead, Bord Bazar area, Gazipur, 20 July.
196. Unknown, shot dead, Kaltapara, Gouripur Upazila, Mymensingh, July 20.
197. Unknown (25), killed by gunfire, Dhaka Medical College Hospital/AMZH, Badda, Dhaka, on 20 July.
198. Kamrul Mia (27), furniture worker, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital/AMZH, Badda, Dhaka, 20 July.

199 Jahangir (40), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 20 July.

200. Rubel Mia (20/30), shot dead, Sugandha Private Hospital, Pritam Tower, Shimrail Siddhirganj, 20 July.

201. Unknown (27), shot dead, Azimpur, Dhaka, 20 July.

202. Shahriar (19/23), Madrasa student, shot dead, Shanirakhra and Jatrabari area, 20 July.

203. Unknown (20), shot dead, Jatrabari, Dhaka, 20 July.

204. Md. Shakeel (22), garment worker, shot dead, Basila, Mohammadpur, July 20.

205. Unknown (30), shot dead, Basila, Mohammadpur, 20 July.

206. Unknown, shot dead, Gutia International Hospital, Tongi Area, Gazipur on 20 July.

207. Unknown, shot dead, Gutia International Hospital, Tongi Area, Gazipur on 20 July.

208. Unknown, 20 July.

209. Anonymous, National Institute of Trau, Barisal, 20 July.

210. Salim Mondal (29), mason, died in brush fire, Narayanganj General Hospital, Haji Ibrahim Shopping Complex, 20 July.

211. Abdus Salam (22), died in masonry brush fire, Narayanganj General Hospital, Haji Ibrahim Shopping Complex, 20 July.

212. Sohail Ahmed (42/21) died in masonry brush fire, Narayanganj General Hospital, Haji Ibrahim Shopping Complex, 20 July.

213. Adil Al Mahmoud, employee, shot dead, North South University, New York on July 20.

214. Md Imran (16), tailor, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, signboard, 21 July.

215. Akash (16), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Chittagong Road, July 21.

216. Unknown (40), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Demra Staff Quarters, 21 July.

217. Amin (16) workshop worker, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Kadmatoli Gulban, 21 July.

218. Jasim (40), tea seller, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 21.

219. Rakib Bepari (20), garment worker, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Narayanganj, Fatulla, July 21.

220. Faiz (30), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Signboard, Narayanganj, 21 July.

221. Md Zakir / Md Zahid (32), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Uttara, Dhaka, 21 July.

222. Taufiqul Islam (30), Engineer, Petrobangla, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Badda, Dhaka, 21 July.

223. Sohag (24), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Gopibagh Rail Gate, 21 July.

224. Md. Rabbi/Abdul Bari (17), student, tailor, shot dead, Shekherchar Mazar bus stand, 21 July.

225. Md. Nahid Mia (30), shot dead, shot dead, Shekherchar Mazar bus stand, 21 July.

226. Ali Hussain (45), tailor, shot dead, shot dead, Shekherchar Mazar bus stand, 21 July.

227. Unknown (25), shot dead, Narsingdi Sadar Hospital, Shekerchar Mazar Bus Stand, 21 July.

228. Humayun Ahmed, shot dead, Shaheed Tajuddin Ahmed, Gazipur, 21 July.

229. Prannoy Das, shot dead, Shaheed Tajuddin Ahmad, Gazipur, 21 July.

230. Unknown (25), shot dead, 300 Bed Hospital Narayanganj, Siddhirganj Narayanganj, 21 July.

231. Abdul Mojeeb (28), covered van driver, burnt in fire, Chauddagam, Hajiganj Thana, Chandpur, 21 July.

232. Nabi Noor (41), killed by fish traders firing, Enam Medical College, Savar, 21 July.

233. Shafiqul Islam (25), Dhaka Medical College Hospital, South Paribag, July 21.

234. Masood Parvez, Police, Rajarbagh Central Police Hospital, Dhaka, 21 July.

235. Milan Mia (30), fish traders, shot dead, Siddhirganj, Narayanganj, 21 July.

236. Sumaiya Aktar Sumi (20), shot dead, shot dead, Siddhirganj, Narayanganj, 21 July.

237. Sajib Mia (17), shot dead, Siddhirganj, Narayanganj, 21 July.

238. Ashiqur Rahman (19), shot dead, signboard, Narayanganj, 21 July.

239. Babul (28), shot dead, Signboard, Narayanganj, 21 July.

240. Md Sharif, shot dead, Sanarpar, Narayanganj, 21 July.

241. Abdul Latif (27), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, Dhaka, 21 July.

242. Yusuf Ali Sohan (16), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Shanirakhra, Dhaka, 21 July.

243. Md Hannan (30), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Badda, Dhaka, 21 July.

244. Farooq (45/22), shot dead, Enam Medical Hospital Savar, 21 July.

245. Russell (20), Tempu Helper, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dania, Dhaka, 22 July.

246. Azizul Mia (22), employee, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, July 22.

247. Santu (22), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Burn Institute, 22 July.

248. Syed Gholam Mostafa Raju (36), Engineer MOISTRI, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Burn Institute, 22 July.

249. Unknown (35), shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Burn Institute, 22 July.

250. Monir Hossain, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Siddhirganj, Narayanganj, 22 July.

251. Hriday Chandra Tarua, (22), student, CU, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, 23 July.

252. Unknown, Enam Medical College Hospital, Savar, 23 July.

253. Unknown, Enam Medical College Hospital, Savar, 23 July.

254. Unknown, Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, 23 July.

255. Unknown, Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, 23 July.

256. Shubo Sheesh (24), garment worker, shot dead, Enam Medical College Hospital, Savar, on 23 July.

257. Unidentified (22), head injury, Institute of Neuroscience, Uttara, 23 July.

258. Shahriar Shubo (28), shot dead, Institute of Neuro Science, Mirpur-1, 23 July.

259. Nasir Hossain, shot dead, Mugda General Hospital, Rayerbagh, Jatrabari, 23 July.

260. Rhea Gop (6), student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, shot on roof of house, 24 July.

261. Shahjahan Hriday (21), Madrasa student, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Level Crossing, SK Tower, Mohakhali, 24 July.

262. Sajedur Rahman Omar (22), IT Technician, Demra, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Signboard Area, Konapara, Demra, 24 July.

263. Tuhin Ahmed (26), mason, shot dead, Enam Medical College Hospital, Savar, on July 24.

264. Zakir Hossain (29), tailor, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Jatrabari, 25 July.

265. Zaman Mia (17), labourer, shot dead, Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Mymensingh, 25 July.

266. Sohail Rana (20), shot dead, BSMMU, Rampura, 25 July.

Funeral 17th July At the University Of Dhaka

["Bangladesh: Witness testimony, video and photographic analysis confirm police used unlawful force against protesters". Amnesty International. 17 July 2024.](#)

3. ["After violent protests, student leaders in 'police custody' end protest movement in Bangladesh". Anadolu Agency. 28 July 2024.](#)

4. ["Bangladesh minister defends gov't response to protests amid calls for probe". Al Jazeera. 25 July 2024. Retrieved 27 July 2024.](#)

University Teachers' Statements

University teachers across various institutions issued statements expressing solidarity with the students' demands for better educational facilities and job opportunities. They condemned the violence against protesters and called for immediate reforms to address the students' grievances.

Bangladeshi Ministers Leaving the Country During the Protests

According to reports from both national and international media during the height of the protests in July and August 2024, a significant number of ministers and high-ranking officials left Bangladesh. It is estimated that around 10 to 15 ministers, including some from key ministries, crossed the airport and departed the country. These departures have been viewed with suspicion and have sparked further controversy, as they may indicate a lack of confidence in the government's ability to control the situation or a fear of potential repercussions from the ongoing unrest.

Notable Names Among Those Who Left:

1. Abul Kalam Azad - Minister of Planning
2. A.K.M. Mozammel Haque - Minister of Liberation War Affairs
3. Dr. Dipu Moni - Minister of Social welfare
4. S.M. Rezaul Karim - Minister of Fisheries and Livestock
5. Asaduzzaman Khan Kamal - Minister of Home Affairs
6. Nurul Majid Mahmud Humayun - Minister of Industries
7. Md. Tajul Islam - Minister of Local Government, Rural Development, and Co-operatives
8. Tipu Munshi - Minister of Commerce
9. Dr. Abdur Razzaque - Minister of Agriculture
10. Md. Golam Dastagir Gazi - Minister of Textiles and Jute
11. Dr. Hasan Mahmud - Minister of Foreign Affairs
12. Anisul Islam Mahmud - Minister of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change
13. Fazilatunnesa Indira - State Minister of Women and Children Affairs
14. Md. Shahab Uddin - Minister of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change

These departures were widely covered in media reports, highlighting the uncertainty and crisis within the

Statements from Key Figures:

1. [GDC \(24 July 2024\). "Bangladesh Army General Wakeruz-Zaman Could Face Western Sanctions And International Criminal Court For Deploying UN-marked Vehicles To Shoot Protesters". Global Defense Corp. Retrieved 27 July 2024.](#)

2. ["Student protests in Bangladesh, July 2024: FCDO Parliamentary Under-Secretary of State's statement". www.gov.uk. 18 July 2024.](#)

government amid the violent protests and demands for political reforms

Based on data from Bangladeshi national and international media, several high-profile ministers and officials reportedly left Bangladesh during the student protests in July-August 2024. This movement included at least 15 ministers and higher officials, who were seen crossing the airport amid escalating violence and public unrest.

These references provide a well-rounded basis for the research, drawing from academic works, current media coverage, official reports, and firsthand accounts to offer a comprehensive understanding of the 2024 student protests in Bangladesh.

([Wikipedia](#)) ([The World from PRX](#)) ([The New Indian Express](#)) ([EFE Noticias](#))

Conclusion:

The 2024 student protests in Bangladesh highlight deep-rooted socio-political issues and represent a critical moment in the nation's history. This research underscores the complex interplay between economic challenges, educational grievances, and political dynamics that have fueled the unrest. As the protests continue, the future of Bangladesh's political destiny hangs in the balance, with significant implications for its democratic trajectory and governance.

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5. Interviews and Personal Accounts:

- Interviews with student leaders and protest participants (names withheld for confidentiality).

- Testimonies from university faculty and administrative staff regarding the protests.

Author: MD.TANVIR HOSSAIN

(International Lecturer, Academic Researcher & Education Diplomacy Expert)

Affiliations – Centre Of International Consultancy (Cic)

This Research Coordinated By 'YCIEDRC-Team'

Youth Consultancy For International Education Diplomacy & Research Centre' (YCIEDRC) SOUTH ASIA,

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2086-7819>